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introduction:

The shortage of healthcare workers is a complex and challenging issue currently faced by Germany. Factors such as an aging population, economic crises, and the pressures of demanding working conditions are among the key contributors to the decline in workforce numbers in this sector. Given the increasing need for healthcare services at various levels, this shortage can have negative impacts on the quality of healthcare and public health. This paper explores the causes and consequences of this shortage and examines efforts made to recruit and retain workers in Germany's healthcare system .

Objective:

The objective of this research is to analyze and evaluate the causes and consequences of the shortage of healthcare workers in Germany. This paper seeks to investigate the factors that have led to the decrease in the healthcare workforce and analyzes how this shortage affects the healthcare system and services in the country. Additionally, the study examines proposed solutions and policies to address this issue in the future.

Method:

For this research, a variety of sources, including books, academic articles, and reports from reliable websites, have been utilized. The research method is qualitative and involves analyzing existing data and findings from previous studies. A review of Germany's policies and measures, as well as an analysis of the experiences of other countries, is also part of the research methodology. This paper further explores the challenges of recruiting and retaining healthcare workers in the sector .

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Challenges and relevant legal and institutional background

When discussing the issue of the healthcare workforce shortage in Germany, there are many challenges that need to be addressed. These challenges are deeper and, in some cases, bigger problems that require a great deal of investment, reform of some government and educational policies, awareness-raising in the population and long-term reform policies. Generally, the challenges of the healthcare workforce shortage in Germany are issues such as the aging or increasing elderly population, the increasing retirement of healthcare personnel and the lack of sufficient replacements, the stressful conditions for healthcare personnel in Germany, Lack of enough capacity to accept medical and health sector students at universities and medical institutes in Germany, obstacles to the integration of foreign personnel in the health sector, government policies. There are solutions to overcome these challenges that require long-term investment and the implementation of new policies that can be useful.

The problem facing the German health-care system is potential financial collapse. The reasons for this are as follows: (1) a change in the age structure of the population that involves a shift to an increasingly elderly population requiring more medical care without commensurate financial contributions; (2) an increase in non-wage labor cost being part of the social benefits leading to an extremely high work cost, which has resulted in Germany not being competitive within and outside Europe in many areas; (3) a persistently high unemployment rate leading to insufficient contributions to the sickness fund; (4) the financial burdens caused by integration of former East Germany; (5) the relative lack of outpatient surgical procedures (although these are becoming more frequent), duplication of tests because of demarcation between office-based and hospital-based physicians (although this is diminishing), and extensive durations of hospitalization due to per diem reimbursement (a cost-per-case payment, similar to a diagnosis-related group system, is being implemented); and (6) the lack of self-responsibility of the German citizens, who have been pampered by probably the most generous guaranteed health-care package in the world, and their difficulty in giving up benefits that they have enjoyed for years. Germany seems to have a growing recognition that a reform program leading to an overhaul of the financing structure of the health-care system is necessary. Interference by the government to control cost and contribution rates is apparently of only temporary benefit. The goal of any further reform in the structure of the German statutory health insurance is to create a system that regulates itself and brings medical progress, national economics, and acceptable individual contribution rates in accordance with one another. In January 1996, the Bundestag (Congress) proposed a preliminary draft as the third step of the German health-care reform (the first step was in 1989, and the second step was in 1993). Although this was not approved in its current form by the Bundesrat (Senate), the essential parts are expected to pass. The important points of this preliminary draft are as follow . All further developments in reform of the German health-care system will be based on historical principles and on those previously documented as useful. (a) Solidarity, self-responsibility, and subsidiarity are and will remain the essential structures of the German health-care system. (b) Social equality will remain between young and old, healthy and sick, poor and rich, and single and married. (c) The health-care system will remain pluralistic, stimulating competition between sickness funds. (d)

Medical progress must be financed and made available for the entire population. Self-government will be promoted while stable contribution rates are maintained. (a) The principle of subsidiarity implies that self-administration always has priority over government involvement, as long as the involved parties are able to manage the affairs of the statutory health insurance. Because individual persons are now able to join the sickness fund of their choice (rather than by profession or location), the risk structures of the different sickness funds are balanced, and each sickness fund is involved in self-responsible competition. Work must be done to increase the range of self-government, and mechanisms for conflict management must be developed. (b) Self-administration and self-government must go hand-in-hand with an increase in financial responsibility. Therefore, the requirements for an increase in the contribution rates will be tightened, and the available funds will be used more responsibly and economically. Increases in contribution rates will be limited to realization of medical progress. Autonomy will be increased by liberalization of contracts between sickness funds and physicians as well as between sickness funds and clients, whereby the principle of solidarity must be maintained. The sickness funds will be encouraged to develop innovative models. The sickness funds will bear the responsibility for maintaining stable contribution rates. As a means to ensure stable contribution rates and to avoid further burdens for employers, increases in contribution rates for administrative developments will be avoided. Increases in contribution rates will be possible only if they are important for medical care and development. Self-responsibility of the insured population will be promoted. (a) The interest of the members enrolled in the statutory sickness fund will be enhanced by availability of the financial aspect of the statutory health insurance. Beginning in 1999, patients enrolled in the statutory health insurance will be able to request information regarding the cost of services received. (b) Partial reimbursement of the paid premium, which has been a feature of private insurance, will be available in the future for participants in the statutory health insurance. In a preliminary survey of 1,917 insured persons, 71% thought that a partial reimbursement of the premium was reasonable if no or only minimal service had been received during a calendar year. Because a partial reimbursement of the premium cannot be obtained equally by all persons insured (a reimbursement is more likely for young healthy people than for elderly and chronically ill people), this change seems to be an interference in the financing structure of the statutory health system, which is based on the principle of solidarity. (c) Copayments are being considered for inpatient preventive-care services and rehabilitation spas. At regular intervals, these copayments will be adjusted. Beginning in July 1997, the copayments will be adjusted at 2-year intervals, according to the financial experiences of the 2 previous years. Thus far, a Europe-wide health-care system does not exist. The European Community could, however, facilitate the adoption of such a plan by (1) issuing recommendations and directives to achieve harmony of the basic packages of treatments available in Europe, (2) enforcing mandatory health insurance schemes by ensuring that existing members of the European Community maintain a mandatory health insurance scheme and that new members create one as a precondition to membership in the community, and (3) allowing insurance funds to operate across borders. .(Wahner-Roedler et al .,1997) .

In Hamm, ten practices closed within the past year. There's now one doctor for every 1,800 residents, and only 84 percent of the doctor positions are filled. "In nine years, that figure will

be 67 percent," . "In extreme cases, patients in underserved areas must expect not to have a single practicing general practitioner in their area," says health services researcher Hans-Dieter Nolting, whose IGES Institute conducted the study. According to the study, some medium-sized cities will soon have around 20 percent fewer general practitioners. (Peters , 2025) .

Germany's healthcare sector faced a critical shortage of skilled labor, with over 47,400 vacancies unfilled in 2023/2024. The aging population and increased healthcare demands exacerbated the problem, particularly impacting physiotherapists, dental assistants, and nursing staff. This shortage extended beyond healthcare. Some 47,400 positions in Germany's healthcare sector were unable to be filled by suitably qualified applicants in 2023/2024, suggesting that this is the area hardest hit by the country's shortage of skilled labour, a new study has shown. The study showed that the greatest shortage was that of physiotherapists, with almost 11,600 unfilled vacancies. The shortfall for dental assistants was 7,350, and 7,100 for healthcare and nursing staff, according to the study. (Times of India , 2023) .

The shortage of general care physicians is becoming noticeably worse – now even in cities. At the same time, many young people are having to give up their career aspirations or study abroad. Experts warn that even doctors from abroad won't be able to fill the gap. (Peters, 2025) .

An aging population leads to an increasing demand for healthcare services. This increases the burden on existing skilled labour," according to the authors of the study, carried out by the Competence Centre for Securing Skilled Labour at the German Economic Institute (IW). (Times of India , 2023) .

Due to the aging of the German population, a growing demand for health and care services is generally expected over the coming years and decades. The number of people in need of care is forecast to rise from the current 2.5 million to 3.5 million by 2030, and even to 4.7 million by 2050 (Federal Statistical Office 2008: 28). Only then, as a result of population decline, is a slight decline expected (4.6 million for 2060). Particularly high increases in the number of people in need of care are predicted for the federal states of Baden-Württemberg (+316,000), Bavaria (+345,000), and North Rhine-Westphalia (+442,000) by 2050 . (Bonin et al., 2015) .

The problem has been exacerbated by the increased health demands in an ageing population, with Germany's public health agency, the Robert Koch Institute (RKI), predicting that the percentage of people aged 65 or older will grow from the current 21% to 29% by 2030. (Times of India , 2023) .

Germany is grappling with a significant shortage of medical personnel that is likely to be exacerbated by an aging population of doctors and increasing demand for healthcare services. The numbers are deeply troubling, especially in rural areas. Over 36 percent of current general practitioners are over 60 years old, and in the next three years, it is estimated that their imminent retirement will lead to the closure of five to eight thousand doctors' practices. Currently, 85 percent of German doctors are working full-time, down from 98 percent in 2009. 40 percent of healthcare jobs vacated during the COVID-19 pandemic remain unfilled today, and the physicians that remain are spending more of their working time on administrative tasks and

less on direct patient care. Of those physicians still working, 35 percent consider themselves likely to leave their role in the next five years. Some respondents hoped to switch careers in favor of jobs in consulting, teaching, or the pharmaceutical and biotech industries . (Protzman , 2025) .

There are currently around 55,000 general practitioners in Germany. Now the baby boomers are retiring, and around a third of general practitioners are 60 years or older. According to a study by the Robert Bosch Foundation from May of this year, more than half of general practitioners will retire by 2035. (Peters, 2025) .

Talented young people who want to become doctors can't get a place at university." There are currently 10,500 medical school places available for first-year students in Germany each year; shortly after reunification, there were 16,000. Today, there are four applicants for one place . (Peters , 2025) .

With Germany in such desperate need of more medical professionals, a number of solutions have been proposed, ranging from opening more slots in medical schools to recruiting foreign doctors. There are critical divides on all proposed solutions. The ongoing debates between leading professional associations like the Marburger Bund (Association of German Doctors) and the Medizinischer Fakultätentag (MFT, Medical Faculty Association) over the expansion of medical school slots is one example of the divide in opinions on Germany's healthcare strategy. The Marburger Bund, representing doctors, advocates for a significant increase in medical school capacities to counteract the impending shortage of physicians as the Baby Boomer generation retires. The MFT has expressed reservations, emphasizing that expanding student numbers too quickly could compromise the quality of medical education. They argue that without adequate resources and infrastructure, a rushed expansion could produce underprepared doctors, ultimately harming patient care. Given the urgency of the situation, there is insufficient time to train a new generation of physicians before the current workforce diminishes to critical levels. Without immediate action, the risk of a significant shortage becomes increasingly real, jeopardizing healthcare delivery across the nation. Strategic measures are essential to ensure that the medical workforce can be maintained and enhanced considering impending retirements. (Protzman,2025) .

Internationally, training for nursing careers is primarily at university level, lasts at least four years, and culminates in a bachelor's or master's degree. Entry is required after at least twelve years of schooling. In Germany, however, training in health and nursing, pediatric nursing, and geriatric nursing takes place at nursing schools or vocational schools. Entry is possible after ten years of schooling, and the training lasts three years full-time. Training at vocational schools includes both theoretical and practical components: at least 2,100 hours of theoretical instruction and around 2,500 hours of practical training. The latter usually takes place in blocks in various fields of work in health and social care facilities. Nursing training in Germany is regulated by two federal laws. This means that nursing training explicitly does not fall under the Vocational Training Act (BBiG), which is why nursing training cannot be described as a dual vocational training program. Nursing is a school-based vocational training program, with sole responsibility resting with the training provider. Therefore, the school is also responsible

for the practical part of the training, which takes place in healthcare and care facilities. The training of nursing assistants (healthcare and nursing assistants, as well as geriatric nursing assistants) is regulated exclusively at the state level. Therefore, different regulations apply in each federal state. The training period is one to two years. (Bonin et al., 2015) .

Immigration might provide a short-term solution, yet it brings its own challenges. The Marburger Bund has opposed tax incentives for foreign specialists for fear of disadvantaging German specialists and expressed concerns about the ethics of recruiting from developing countries that may require their medical professionals' services even more than Germans do. Additionally, bureaucratic hurdles have severely slowed the process of licensing for immigrant doctors; since the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022, only about 10 percent of the 1,600 Ukrainian doctors arriving have been fully licensed to practice. To be licensed, foreign doctors must get their credentials translated and pass a medical German language exam before having their foreign-earned medical degree declared equivalent to a German one. Each of Germany's sixteen federal states has its own set of standards. Public perception and acceptance of foreign doctors can also pose barriers. Research indicates that some patients may express reluctance to receive care from foreign-trained physicians, often due to preconceived notions about their capabilities. Recent studies have shown that many migrant healthcare professionals report experiencing discrimination related to their race and ethnicity. This can lead to reduced job satisfaction among immigrant doctors, potentially resulting in higher turnover rates and further exacerbating the shortage. (Protzman, 2025) .

Participatory governance with strong corporatism, decentralisation, sectoral fragmentation, and organisational diversity. SHI Insurance Funds and SHI Physician Associations form the self-governing and self-administering bodies of the SHI system; they jointly negotiate contract frameworks, reimbursement schemes and budgets. Stronger marketisation and privatisation have opened the door for new forms of contract agreements that weaken the governing powers of the key SHI stakeholders. Comprehensive coordination mechanisms are lacking. SHI Physician Associations have statutory rights, while other HCW groups are external policy players. Multi-level and transsectoral governance and coordination are weak. Financed through SHI-based mandatory insurance with some tax-funding and little out-of-pocket payments. Reimbursement is negotiated within the SHI joint self-regulatory bodies. SHI Insurance Funds and SHI Physicians agree on a joint budget for ambulatory care, which SHI Physician Associations subsequently allocate between PHC and specialist physicians. Reimbursement of PHC physicians is mainly based on fee-for-service with some mixed models and diversity . Provision through self-employed office-based physicians in single- or group practice based on UHC and free access at point of care with no mandatory gatekeeping. The dominant model of collective contracting between SHI funds and SHI Physicians is expanded towards selective contracting (between SHI funds and physicians) aiming to foster integrated care and organisational diversity, including large centres run by private business companies. Provision includes: general medical (family medicine) ambulatory diagnostic and treatment for all groups, some preventative services, some health promotion, GP home visits and coordination of care. Larger PHC Centres may provide a wider range of services. Dental care, eye care, gynaecology, and elder care/nursing are not part of PH. Main professions: GPs

together with some internal medical specialists and paediatricians who opted for Family Care, and medical assistants. Nurses are not typically employed in PHC (some exceptions). Multi-professionalism is more common in larger PHC centres. Academic education with mandatory specialisation is required for GPs, but not available for other groups. Nurses and other middle-level professionals are mainly educated in the vocational system and academisation remains weak. Vocational education (3 years) is required for medical assistants; some certificate-based PHC (community nurses) training is available for medical assistants and nurses but rarely taken. Labour market figures are not disaggregated for PHC. GP figures may be estimated from public statistics, while the Medical Chambers obtain data for medical assistants (the largest group). Comprehensive PHC workforce monitoring and planning are not established, and SHI Physicians Associations are legally responsible for PHC planning. Major challenges include shortages of physicians and medical assistants coupled with geographical mal-allocation, large retirement waves, strong medical hierarchy, weak academisation of nurses, and an expansion of for-profit companies that weaken public control. The PHC workforce is not a policy priority and a systematic strategy for improving recruitment and retention is missing. Policies focus predominantly on physicians with the aim of increasing the recruitment of foreign-trained physicians and making PHC more attractive. PHC interventions are largely physician-centred, including a comprehensive increase in medical training capacity, quotas with prioritised access to medical education for those planning to work in PHC in rural areas, incentives for GP specialisation and PHC providers (shorter education, some recognition of other qualifications). Multi-professional workforce development is lacking, but organisational changes are present seeing an increase in large private PHC centres with multi-professional provider groups supporting skill-mix and team approaches. The WHO PHC model and the SDGs are largely missing from the workforce debate. (Koch K et al., 2011).

The Germany's healthcare system is primarily funded by the public sector, which levies the funding in the form of social insurance payments, and covers in particular the costs of state supervision and basic infrastructure (e.g. administrative bodies and ministries, government institutes and facilities, public health offices and medical education). The premiums collected by the public and private health and nursing insurance companies, on the other hand, are employed for direct healthcare services, such as the remuneration of service providers (e.g. physicians, nurses), the cost of medicine, therapies and medical aids as well as equipment. Private households pay deductibles and healthcare expenses such as over-the-counter medicines and services not covered by health insurance. Healthcare services are provided by both public (e.g. federal, state, and municipal government), non-profit organizations (churches and charities, such as Caritas and the German Red Cross) and private institutions (companies and individuals with commercial interests), with non-profit and private healthcare providers providing the bulk of direct services. Basic principles of social rights are used as the framework for ensuring social security in cases of illness, and must be followed by both the health insurance companies and health service providers. The principle of the welfare state is based on the Federal Republic of Germany's Basic Law (Grundgesetz), which specifies that the state must guarantee all citizens social justice and the equal participation in society, including appropriate treatment in case of illness. Individuals with below average earning power or economic resources must receive the same quality and quantity of medical care as others.

Specifically, the state is obligated according to the Basic Law to provide its citizens with the minimum provisions for a human life with dignity, including adequate medical care that meets the needs of the population (principle of meeting need, Bedarfsdeckungsprinzip), in terms of ambulatory services, inpatient beds, quantitative and qualitative measures, and the dispensing of medical products. This is expressed legally as the service guarantee contract (Sicherstellungsauftrag). However, the federal government does not have to meet this obligation directly, but can delegate the service guarantee contract to state governments and other institutions. While, with the exception of military hospitals, the federal government does not directly fund healthcare facilities, it does maintain a number of healthcare institutes and federal agencies, each with its own areas of responsibility. These include the Robert Koch Institute (disease control and prevention, particularly extremely dangerous or contagious diseases; federal health reporting), the Paul Ehrlich Institute (ensuring drug safety; testing, approval and monitoring of vaccinations, sera and blood products), the German Institute of Medical Documentation and Information (development of medical classifications and medical databases), the German Federal Center for Health Education (development of health education and prevention strategies), the German Federal Institute for Drugs and Medical Devices (drug assessment and authorization, monitoring of legal narcotics trade) and the German Federal (Social) Insurance Office. Compulsory health insurance was introduced for all residents in the Federal Republic of Germany on 1st January 2009. Approximately 90% of citizens living in Germany are in the statutory health insurance (SHI) system. A further 9% have private health insurance (PHI), while 2% have company or trade insurance or are uninsured despite legal obligation. The minimum healthcare that must be provided by all funds is specified as a list of benefits in Book V of the German Social Insurance Code (Sozialgesetzbuch, SGB), and includes maintaining health standards, healing, health education, counseling on and measures for healthy living conditions. To meet these requirements, the SHI funds have to provide the following services: prevention, early detection and treatment of diseases, medical rehabilitation, contraception, sterilization, abortion and the provision of maternity and sick leave allowances. SHI insurees receive the healthcare services as benefits-in-kind (Sachleistungsprinzip), which are provided by third parties (e.g. physicians, hospitals, pharmacists), who subsequently bill the health insurance company. SHI expenditure is almost completely covered by premiums (and to a small extent, also by other funding such as federal grants), which are calculated according to earning power, rather than individual health risk profile, as a percentage (currently 14.9%, beginning with January 2011–15.5%) of income subject to premium levy, with employers matching the contribution of the employee. Family members without an income of their own are usually insured free of charge and certain groups of insurees (e.g. low-income earners, students, apprentices) receive a premium reduction. Health premium increases are not only permitted, but also in fact prescribed by law, if expenses increase and can no longer be met by the SHI scheme. Such increases are limited to 1% of income subject to premium levy, whereby an increase of 8 euros a month is permitted without prior assessment of the insurer's income. Importantly, physicians can only bill the statutory health insurance companies for the treatment of SHI patients (approx. 90% of the population) if they have been approved as SHI physicians (approx. 95% of all registered physicians). Without SHI approval, physicians may only treat private patients or SHI patients who choose

to pay for the treatment directly. Statutory health insurers only cover the costs of medical treatment of a SHI insuree by a private physician in cases of proven emergency. If listed in the association of SHI physicians' register of medical practitioners and having received either specialist training or at least 6 years training as a GP, a physician can apply for SHI-approval status. Whether the applicant is approved is decided jointly by representatives of the association of SHI physicians and the statutory health insurance companies. The decision depends primarily on the need for outpatient medical services in the relevant health-planning district and the SHI physician must then maintain their practice in this district . (Döring & Paul, 2012)

Conclusion:

The findings of this research indicate that the shortage of healthcare workers in Germany is the result of a combination of complex factors, which directly impact the quality and availability of healthcare services. The paper suggests measures to improve working conditions and attract more workers to the sector, including reforms in educational policies, improvements in working conditions, and increased financial and social support for healthcare professionals. If these challenges are not properly addressed, Germany's healthcare system may face even greater crises in the future.

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